

Relation Between Kaniadakis and Tsallis Entropies

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It is well known that Shannon's entropy is: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ and that $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, such that extremization of Shannon's entropy with respect to $p(e_i)$ and subject to the constraints $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$, yield the MB result. One may also note that in this case, $\ln(p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized}) = -e_i/T$.

If one mathematically wished to create a function $\ln_k(p)$ such that only powers of p to k or $-k$ appear and $\ln_k \rightarrow \ln$ when $k \rightarrow 0$, then one might also wish to write such an entropy as: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln_k(p(e_i))$. The math function which satisfies the above rules is the well-known Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p) = \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} / (2k)$. For $\ln_k(p) = -e_i/T$, $p(e_i) = \{ \sqrt[k]{1 + k(e_i/T)} - k(e_i/T) \}^{-1/k}$. One possible issue with this approach is that one can no longer use the usual variational approach with the Shannon constraints to obtain $p(e_i)$. Furthermore, it is not clear what the physical meaning is of p^k or p^{-k} . p^k might be considered as a product of probabilities, but p^{-k} is unusual.

As a result, one might wonder if there exists a single parameter expression with a $\ln_q(p) = -e_i/T$ again, but with perhaps a different function, $f(p, q)$ weighting $\ln_q(p)$ such that one may apply a variational process. (For $q=1$, $f(p, q) = p$.) Furthermore, for interpretative reasons it might be good if only p^q appears because this has a physical meaning. Furthermore, we wish this function to be part of an extremization process, which we argue is linked with stability of the average of information.

We consider here that even though the Kaniadakis form does not have the properties discussed in the above paragraph, a form, equivalent to $\sum p \ln_k(p)$, does with one modification, namely that the Kaniadakis form is equal to: $p^q (p^{2(1-q)} - 1) / [2(1-q)]$ and if the 2 were replaced with 1, all of the requirements of the previous paragraph would be met.

Kaniadakis Entropy

As we have noted before, Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis schemes are based on the existence of an information function:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((1))$$

In Shannon's case it is $\ln(p)$, in the Tsallis case, $\ln_q(p)$ and in the Kaniadakis case, $\ln_k(p)$.

Let us consider obtaining the Kaniadakis form in the following mathematical way. We insist on ((1)) and then argue that there may only appear p to the power of k or $-k$ and for $k \rightarrow 0$ $F(p) = \ln(p)$. A math solution is:

$$\ln_k(p) = \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} / (2k) \quad ((2))$$

l'Hopital's rule is used in the $k \rightarrow 0$ case. One may next write an entropy (as in (1)) as:

$$S_k = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln_k(p(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

The problem with ((3)), however, is that extremizing it subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total}$ does not yield the required:

$$p(e_i) = \left\{ \frac{1 + k(e_i/T)}{1 + k} \right\}^{-1/k} \quad ((4))$$

Furthermore, physically it is difficult to interpret p^{-k} .

We thus ask: Is there another single parameter scheme with only p^{-q} such that one has $\ln q(e_i/T) = -e_i/T$ and $q \rightarrow \text{constant}$ yield $\ln(p)$ together with an entropy:

$$f(p, q) \ln q(p) \text{ such that } q \rightarrow \text{constant} \quad f(p, q) = p^{-q} \quad ((5))$$

exist? This result should only contain p^{-q} and should lead to a variational process of ((5)) subject to $\sum_i p(e_i) = \text{constant}$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^{-q} = \text{constant}^2$ yielding $\exp q(e_i/T)$ such that $\ln q(\exp q(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$.

As a first test, one may consider manipulating the Kaniadakis entropy to see if this sheds any light on the matter.

A New (Tsallis Actually) Distribution

In the Kaniadakis case:

$$S_k = - \sum_i p(e_i) \left\{ p^k - p^{-k} \right\} / (2k) \quad ((6))$$

$$p^{-k} p^k - p^k p^{-k} / (2k)$$

$$= p^{-q} \left\{ p^{2(1-q)} - 1 \right\} / (2(1-q)) \quad ((7))$$

Here $1-q = k$. The form ((7)) is interesting in that it $f(p) = p^{-q}$, which has a physical interpretation for $q = \text{positive integer}$. The problem is that the Kaniadakis case does not follow from a simple variation of $p \ln_k(p)$ and neither does ((7)) Furthermore, entropy contains p^{-q} and p^{-q} because of the factor 2, but it would not if 2 were replaced with 1. In both cases, the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit yields $p \ln(p)$.

If one simply uses the one parameter q case such that one has an expression which becomes $p \ln(p)$ for $q \rightarrow 1$ and $\ln q(p) = -e_i/T$ always, then one may examine whether this follows from a variational principle, namely:

$$\text{Extremization of } p^{-q} \left\{ p^{(1-q)} - 1 \right\} / (1-q) - e_i/T p(e_i)^{-q} - b p(e_i) \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{For } b=1, \text{ one obtains: } p(e_i) = \left\{ 1 - (1-q)e_i/T \right\}^{-1/q} \quad ((9))$$

For $q \rightarrow 1$ $p(e)$ becomes $\exp(-e_i/T)$, the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann result. Again, we note that these arguments are based on math and not necessarily on physics. As a start, however, the idea of $p(e_i)$ power q appears and seems to have a physical basis, i.e. there may be a probability $p(e)$ for one event (a seed does not get eaten by a bird) and $p(e_i)$ power q may be another, the probability that it germinates which takes q days. (Here it is assumed it will germinate as long as it is not eaten.)

The next question becomes: Why is one concerned whether $p(e)$ follows from a variational principle or not?

We argued in previous notes that one may consider the stability of:

Sum over i $p_1(e_i)$ power q $F(p(e_i))$ ((10)) which is the average information.

Using $p_1(e_i) \rightarrow p_1(e_i) + dp_1(e_i)$ and $p_1(e_i) = C(T) p(e_i)$ one has still has the requirement that:

$F(p_{new}(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((11)) In other words, one may change $p_1(e_i)$, but ((11)) is always a restriction.

Then $\text{Sum over } i \{p_1(e_i) + dp_1(e_i)\} \text{ power } q (-e_i/T) \text{ approx} = \text{Sum over } i p_1(e_i) (-e_i/T) + q dp_1(e_i) p_1(e_i) \text{ power } (q-1) (-e_i/T)$ ((12))

Now: $\text{Sum over } i e_i p_1(e_i) \text{ power } q = E_{total} \rightarrow \text{Sum over } i dp_1(e_i) e_i q p_1(e_i) \text{ power } (q-1) = 0$ ((13))

So ((12)) equals ((10)) and there is stability.

One may also write: $\text{Sum over } i p_1(e_i) \text{ power } q (-T F(p(e_i)))$ ((14))

Then: $-dT/dp F(p(e_i)) - T dF/dp = 0$ or a variational procedure with: $p \text{ power } q dF/dp = 1$ (i.e. using $p(e_i)$ everywhere and not $p_1(e_i)$) will yield the $\exp q$ distribution. Thus, the variational procedure is argued to hold for stability reasons. In other words, in the extremization process one uses only $p(e_i)$ (which is unnormalized) and assumes T is a constant (i.e. it is a Lagrange multiplier. In ((14)), T is a function of $p(e_i)$, but this approach uses $p_1(e_i)$). The unnormalized $p(e_i)$ approach is consistent with that of Shannon's entropy. One may solve the problem using unnormalized $p(e_i)$ in the entropy expression, even though formally, the entropy and constraints are defined using normalized probabilities. In such a case, one treats $C(T)$, the normalization constant as a constant and considers changes in $p(e_i)$ consistent with a fixed T linked to $E_{total} = N \frac{3}{2} RT$. If E is constant, T is considered constant and one only considers variations of probability consistent with this.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p(e_i)) = \{p(e_i) \text{ power } k - p(e_i) \text{ power } -k\} / (2k)$ does yield $\ln(p)$ for $k \rightarrow 0$, but is not obtainable from a variational principle. We argue that a

variational principle is linked with stability. Furthermore we argue that it is difficult to physically explain p power $-k$. We manipulate Kaniadakis entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln_k(p(e_i))$ and find that it may be written in the suggestive manner: $-\sum_i p(e_i)^q \{ p(e_i)^{2(1-q)} - 1 \} / (2(1-q))$. This is still not linked with a variational process, but replacing 2 with 1 leads to an expression which is and only contains $p(e_i)^q$ which has a physical interpretation as an AND probability.

References

1. Abreu, E. et al. Tsallis and Kaniadakis Statistics from a point of view of the holographic equipartition law (2018)

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.06513>